

АНАЛИЗ СКООДИНИРОВАННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КИТАЯ ПОСРЕДСТВОМ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

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ANALYSIS ON THE COORDINATED DEVELOPMENT OF CHINA'S REGIONAL ECONOMY THROUGH DIGITAL ECONOMY

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Основываясь на истории развития цифровой экономики моей страны, в этой статье используется теория распространения знаний Ромера для построения модели панельных данных для конкретного анализа. Благодаря эмпирическим исследованиям установлено, что цифровая экономика играет важную роль в содействии экономическому росту в различных регионах моей страны. В то же время, посредством регионального экономического анализа и сравнения восточных, центральных и западных регионов, в данной статье показано, что цифровые региональные экономические эффекты в центральных и западных регионах почти одинаковы, а эффекты цифрового экономического роста в двух регионах выше, чем в восточном регионе.

ABSTRACT

Based on the development history of my country's digital economy, this paper uses Romer's knowledge spillover theory to construct a panel data model for specific analysis. Through empirical research, it is found that the digital economy plays an important role in promoting economic growth in various regions of my country. At the same time, through regional economic analysis and comparison of the eastern, central and western regions, this paper finds that the digital regional economic effects in the central and western regions are almost the same, and the digital economic growth effects in the two regions are higher than those in the eastern region.

Ключевые слова: региональная экономика, цифровая экономика, скоординированное развитие.

Keywords: regional economy, digital economy, coordinated development.

INTRODUCTION

With the deepening development of global economic integration and the accelerated advancement of technological innovation, new quality productivity has become a key force in promoting world economic growth. According to a report provided by the Trusted Blockchain and Algorithmic Economic Research Institute of the National Bureau of Statistics, over the past decade, the average annual growth rate of new industries and new formats driven by technological innovation has exceeded 5%, far higher than the average growth rate of global GDP during the same period. This trend not only highlights the important role of new quality productivity in global economic structural adjustment and industrial upgrading, but also highlights its key position in promoting the coordinated development of regional economies (He, Y. 2021). Therefore, in-depth exploration of the development mechanism and action path of high-quality productivity in the regional economy is of great theoretical and practical significance for achieving high-quality economic development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

With the continuous evolution of the global economic landscape, my country's economy has entered a new stage of development - the new normal. Against this background, the digital economy, with its unique

advantages and characteristics, is gradually becoming the core engine and source of power to promote high-quality economic and social development. Compared with the traditional industrial economy and agricultural economy, the digital economy, with its high integration, high participation and high penetration, is profoundly changing the production and lifestyle of mankind and leading a new round of scientific and technological revolution and industrial transformation. As a new economic form, the digital economy has developed at an unprecedented speed and has been widely penetrated into various industries and fields. It has brought new production factors, including digital technologies such as big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence. These technologies are gradually replacing or optimizing traditional production factors and promoting the innovation and upgrading of production methods. Through digital means, we can break geographical restrictions and information barriers, provide the possibility of leapfrog development for underdeveloped regions, and promote these regions to achieve leapfrog economic development by introducing advanced digital technologies and business models. At the same time, the digital economy has also spawned a new management model, which has achieved more efficient integration and allocation of resources through data-driven

and intelligent decision-making. By improving production efficiency, optimizing resource allocation, and stimulating market vitality, the digital economy has injected new impetus into the sustained and healthy development of the economy, and has played a key role in adjusting the industrial structure, promoting industrial upgrading, stimulating domestic market potential, solving the problem of unbalanced and insufficient development, and promoting high-quality economic development. On the one hand, the digital economy has been continuously integrated with the real economy in the process of development, so that the application of digital technology in various industries has gradually released the driving force to promote the upgrading of the industrial structure, which can stimulate the economic development potential of different regions, enable them to develop characteristic industries according to local conditions, and gradually achieve all-round high-quality development in various regions, thereby reducing the development gap between regions. At the same time, the digital economy has also promoted the green and sustainable development of the economy. By promoting innovation and development in fields such as clean energy and intelligent transportation, it has provided strong support for the realization of comprehensive, coordinated and sustainable development of the economy and society. On the other hand, the production factor unique to the digital economy, namely data, has the characteristics of high permeability, which can reset the input ratio of production factors in the production process, improve productivity and production efficiency, and maximize output under the same input, becoming an important driving force for regional coordinated development (Zhong Wen and Zheng Minggui, 2021). So, can the digital economy promote the coordinated development of regional economies? How are its effects manifested? Is the impact of the digital economy on the coordinated development of regional economies at different levels heterogeneous? (Liu, X., & Zhang, X, 2023). In order to answer the above questions, this paper, based on a theoretical analysis of the impact mechanism of the digital economy on the coordinated development of regional economies, uses provincial panel data to test this direct and indirect impact in order to provide a decision-making basis for promoting regional coordinated development.

1. Theory and analysis of digital regional economy

1.1 Theoretical Analysis of Digital Economy

The existing literature on the discussion of the digital economy mainly focuses on two aspects. First, it is about the measurement of the comprehensive index of the digital economy. Some scholars focus on key indicators such as the Internet to characterize the digital economy. For example, Liu Jun et al. (2020) constructed a comprehensive and detailed digital economy measurement framework based on the Internet, digital transactions and informatization. This framework not only covers the infrastructure of the digital economy, but also takes into account the activeness of digital transaction activities and the level of informatization. This comprehensive indicator system has been recog-

nized by many scholars and provides an important reference for us to measure the level of development of the digital economy. Some scholars also refer to the measurement method of the digital economy of the Academy of Information and Communications Technology and measure the digital economy with digital industrialization and industrial digitalization (Yang Huimei and Jiang Lu, 2021). Among them, digital industrialization mainly focuses on the added value of the core industries of the digital economy, reflecting the direct contribution of the digital economy to the national economy; industrial digitalization measures the added value brought by the digital transformation and upgrading of traditional industries, reflecting the enabling role of the digital economy on traditional industries. This measurement method takes into account both the independent development of the digital economy and its deep integration with traditional industries, providing strong support for our comprehensive understanding of the connotation and development trend of the digital economy. Second, the discussion on the mechanism of the digital economy is mainly carried out at three levels. At the micro level. As the core of the digital economy, digital technology and data elements have penetrated into all aspects of economic production activities, which can reduce the cost of production factors and the circulation and transaction costs of factors. By applying digital technology, enterprises can obtain, process and analyze data more efficiently, so as to grasp market demand and production conditions more accurately and optimize production decisions. This not only reduces unnecessary waste of resources, but also reduces production costs, thereby improving the competitiveness of enterprises. At the same time, the introduction of digital technology and data elements also helps enterprises achieve economies of scale and scope in production (Xu Man et al., 2023). Economies of scale mean that as the scale of production expands, the cost of unit products will gradually decrease, thereby improving the economic benefits of enterprises. Economies of scope mean that enterprises can achieve resource sharing and cost sharing through diversified production or services, further reducing costs and improving profitability. At the meso level, the rapid development and widespread application of digital technology are leading the optimization and upgrading of industrial structure. Driven by digital technology, traditional industries are transforming into technology-intensive ones. By introducing advanced digital equipment and systems, the production process has been automated and intelligent, and the technical content and added value of products have been improved. This transformation has not only enhanced the competitiveness of the industry, but also injected new impetus into the long-term development of the industry.

1.2 Theoretical Analysis of Regional Economy

With its unique advantages, the digital economy provides a broader space and more efficient way for financial services, enabling financial services to reach various groups more accurately, especially those areas and people that are difficult to cover with traditional financial services. This increase in inclusiveness will not only help alleviate financial exclusion, but also provide

financing support for more enterprises and individuals, and promote innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth. In addition, the digital economy can significantly reduce the difficulty of cross-regional economic transactions (Chen, N., Wang, S., Zhang et al., 2024). By applying digital technology, the speed of information transmission and processing is greatly accelerated, and the two parties to the transaction can communicate and negotiate more conveniently. These changes make cross-regional economic transactions more flexible and efficient, help overcome spatial barriers to economic development, and promote optimal resource allocation and regional coordinated development.

As a core indicator to measure regional development, the level of economic development is of vital importance in the study of regional coordinated development measurement. Economic cooperative development must not only focus on economic growth, but also pay attention to the connections and economic gaps between various economic sectors in the region. Therefore, the three dimensions of inter-regional economic connections, economic growth and economic differences can comprehensively measure the level of coordinated regional economic development (Qin Chenglin et al., 2011). With the deepening of research on regional coordinated development, some scholars have studied its impact on regional coordination from the perspectives of technological innovation, government competition, market agglomeration, and ecological concepts (Yang Renfa and Shen Chen, 2022). After the rise of the digital economy, many scholars have analyzed the importance of the impact of the digital economy on the coordinated development of regional economies. For example, some scholars have used empirical analysis to affirm its positive role (Wang Zhigang et al., 2024;). As the connotation of the digital economy continues to enrich, scholars only discuss the impact of the digital economy on the coordinated development of regional economies from partial perspectives such as the Internet, network infrastructure, and digital finance, ignoring the complexity, diversity, and systematic measurement of the digital economy itself. Research findings are inevitably limited by the research perspective. Some scholars have also deeply explored the mechanism by which the digital economy affects coordinated regional development. The digital economy can enhance market potential through the consumer side and production side respectively, thereby narrowing the regional economic development gap (Ma Weibiao and Wu Yuming, 2023). The rapid development of the digital economy can reduce regional development gaps by accelerating the marketization of production factors, increasing the circulation speed of factors in the market, and reducing circulation costs. The development of digital technology can increase the enthusiasm and activity of market innovation. Both enterprises and individuals can learn about new innovation results and learn new scientific and technological knowledge at low cost through the Internet and other platforms, thus improving the market's innovation ability and entrepreneurial activity. degree, promote comprehensive economic development and narrow regional development gaps.

In summary, the local perspective of digital economy studies its impact on the coordinated development of regional economy, while from the overall perspective of digital economy, there are few research results that deeply explore its comprehensive impact on the coordinated development of regional economy. Moreover, when exploring the mechanism of action between the two, current research often starts from a single path, ignoring the possible complex and multiple interaction relationship between the two.

Materials and Methods

2 Empirical Analysis of the Impact of Digital Economy on Regional Economic Growth in my country

2.1 Data Model

Based on Romer's knowledge spillover theory, in order to deeply understand the impact of the digital economy on economic growth in various regions of my country, it is necessary to establish a mathematical model. This model will pay special attention to the unique attributes of the digital economy and how it interacts with regional economic growth, and in this way, it will thoroughly explore its impact mechanism (Xu, Y., & Li, A. 2019). The specific composition of the model is as follows:

$$\ln Y_{it} = \alpha \ln L_{it} + \beta \ln K_{it} + \gamma \ln DE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Among them, $\ln Y$ represents the natural logarithm of the total economic volume of the i th region in the t th year. $\ln Y_{it}$ represents the natural logarithm of the number of labor in the i th region in the t th year. $\ln K_{it}$ represents the natural logarithm of the capital stock in the i th region in the t th year. $\ln DE_{it}$ represents the natural logarithm of the digital economy index in the i th region in the t th year. α , β , γ are the parameters to be estimated, representing the elasticity coefficients of labor, capital reserves, and the digital economy on the overall economic effect, respectively. ε_{it} is the error term, representing the impact of other unobserved factors on the total economic volume.

2.2 Research variable selection

This study covers the period from 2013 to 2023, focusing on relevant data from 31 provincial-level administrative units in China (excluding Hong Kong, Macao and Taiwan) to analyze the relationship between the digital economy and regional economic growth.

(1) Economic aggregate: In this study, regional per capita GDP data is used to measure economic aggregate. The above data are mainly sourced from the official website of the National Bureau of Statistics (<https://www.stats.gov.cn/>) and the statistical yearbooks of provinces, cities and districts. At the same time, in order to eliminate the impact of price factors, this paper uses 2014 as the base year to calculate the actual value of per capita GDP in each region.

(2) Labor force: In this study, the labor force indicator used is the employed population in urban units, measured in 10,000 people. The data mainly comes from the official website of the National Bureau of Statistics, which is used to show the labor supply status of various regions.

(3) Capital stock: In order to measure the capital stock of each region, this paper adopts the perpetual inventory method. The calculation formula of capital stock is:

$$K_{it} = \text{total investment}/(g+\delta)$$

In formula (2), g represents the economic growth rate, and δ represents the economic depreciation rate, which is set at 9.6% in this study. The data on total investment are also obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics and the statistical yearbooks of various provinces, cities, and regions.

(4) Digital Economy Index: The construction of the digital economy index will consider multi-dimensional indicators such as Internet penetration rate, degree of digital technology application, and contribution rate of digital industries. Such data mainly come from the National Information Center (<http://www.sic.govcn>), the official website of the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (<https://www.miit.gov.cn/>) and relevant industry reports. Finally, SPASS is used to statistically describe the above variables. The calculation results are shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3. The regression analysis results are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Table 1

Statistical description of data

variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
InY	9.49	1.02	5.98	11.48
InL	5.93	3.88	3.12	7.58
InK	10.46	1.12	6.72	12.6
InE	8.13	1.09	4.38	10.55

Table 2

Overall national perspective

variable \ angle	Nationwide (Fixed Effects)	Central Region (Fixed Effects)	East area (Fixed Effects)	Western Region (Fixed Effects)
oeLh	0.2451*** (0.0211)	0.3346*** (0.0509)	0.1861*** (0.0238)	0.3486*** (0.0469)
InL	0.2271*** (0.0263)	0.2134*** (0.0527)	0.1463** (0.0323)	0.3865*** (0.0605)
InK	0.2535*** (0.0182)	0.1568*** (0.0423)	0.3178*** (0.0222)	0.1375*** (0.0409)
cons	1.4476*** (0.1225)	3.9613*** (0.2802)	4.0813*** (0.1618)	2.8186*** (0.2412)
FExperience	67.62	35.36	82.90	58.36
Hausman test	124.87***	8.89*	43.59**	65.74

Note: The data in brackets are robust standard errors. *** indicates that the data are significant at the 1% significance level; ** indicates that the data are significant at the 5% significance level; and * indicates that the data are significant at the 10% significance level.

Table 3

Regional robustness test

variable \ angle	Nationwide (Fixed Effects)	Central Region (Fixed Effects)	East area (Fixed Effects)	Western Region (Fixed Effects)
oeLh	0.2451*** (0.0211)	0.3346*** (0.1053)	0.1860*** (0.0238)	0.3476*** (0.8580)
InL	0.2216*** (0.0263)	0.2243** (0.0812)	0.1462*** (0.0313)	0.3865*** (0.1019)
InK	0.2540*** (0.1225)	0.1542 (0.0423)	0.3178*** (0.0212)	0.1385*** (0.0479)
R ²	0.9513 0.9793	0.9447 0.8721	0.9776 0.9790	0.9765 0.9606**

Note: The data in brackets are robust cluster standard errors. *** indicates that the data are significant at the 1% significance level; ** indicates that the data are significant at the 5% significance level; and * indicates that the data are significant at the 10% significance level.

Figure 1 Linear regression chart of the whole country and the western region

Figure 2 Linear regression diagram of the eastern and central regions

Results and discussion

According to the data in Table 2, it can be observed that the model has a good fitting effect, and the positive correlation between the digital economy index and regional economic growth (GDP) is confirmed. Nationwide, the coefficient of the digital economy index is 0.2451, which highlights the importance of the digital economy in promoting economic growth. Specifically, every 1% increase in digital economy investment can increase GDP by about 0.25%. At present: With the continuous advancement of technologies such as 5G, artificial intelligence, mobile Internet, cloud computing and big data, the digital economy is entering a new stage of development. At the same time, the data shows that a 1% increase in the labor force can lead to an increase of about 0.23% in GDP, which reflects the important role of the labor force in economic growth.

The central region, including Hebei Province, Liaoning Province, Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, Fujian Province, Shandong Province, Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, Chongqing Municipality and Sichuan Province, has also achieved outstanding results in the development of the digital economy. According to the digital economy index in Table 2, when the digital economy in such regions grows by 1%, GDP is expected to grow by about 0.35%; when labor input increases by 1%, the regional economy is expected to grow by about 0.23%; when capital input increases by 1%, GDP growth is about 0.18%.

The eastern region, including Beijing, Tianjin, Shandong Province and other places, has performed very well in the development of digital economy, especially in the construction resource development and innovation capabilities of digital economic infrastructure. It is in a leading position in the country and has become a pioneer in the development of digital economy.

The western region includes Inner Mongolia, Guangxi, Chongqing and other places. According to the regression analysis results, the digital economy index coefficient of the region is 0.3486, which means that for

every 1% increase in the digital economy, GDP is expected to increase by about 0.35%. In addition, the labor coefficient is 0.3865, indicating that for every 1% increase in labor input, GDP is expected to increase by about 0.39%. The coefficient of capital input is 0.1375, indicating that for every 1% increase in capital, GDP will increase by about 0.14% (Cheng, C., & Huang, H. 2022). These data show that the western region has an urgent need to develop the digital economy and introduce high-skilled digital economy talents.

In general, through the horizontal comparative analysis of the eastern, central and western regions, it can be observed that the coefficients of the digital economy index in the central and western regions are almost the same, and the coefficients of these two regions exceed those of the eastern region. This phenomenon highlights the potential of the digital economy in breaking geographical restrictions and providing more development opportunities for the central and western regions. For example, Qinghai Province, with its superior ecological conditions, vast area and cool climate, has become an ideal location for the construction of a big data base "21. As a major tourist province, Yunnan can promote the transformation and upgrading of Yunnan's tourism industry through the linkage early warning of big data, making it a demonstration city for the application of tourism big data in my country, which not only provides valuable experience for other cities to apply big data in the tourism field, but also injects new impetus into the rapid development of the economy.

In order to verify whether the conclusion is correct, we conducted a robustness test again. According to the results in Table 3, it can be concluded that the parameter coefficients and signs selected in this paper have not changed significantly, indicating that the digital economy and regional economic growth model proposed in this paper is relatively robust and the research conclusion is correct.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, in order to further promote the development of regional economies in China and make full use of the potential of the digital economy, the following conclusions are drawn: The digital economy index coefficient of the eastern region is lower than that of the central and western regions, but the eastern region has obvious advantages in technological innovation and capital accumulation; the central region should continue to take advantage of its development momentum in the digital economy and increase investment in digital technology, especially in key industries such as education and medical manufacturing; the economic development of the western region is relatively lagging due to geographical and historical conditions. Therefore, the government should continue to support the development of the digital economy by formulating favorable policies, providing financial support, and improving the regulatory environment to promote the research and development and application of digital technology. And strengthen coordination and cooperation among regions to ensure that the benefits of the digital economy can be more balanced across the country.

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